

Drawings by Johan Tobias Sergel at Nationalmuseum

Documentation of a guest colleague project

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Drawings by Johan Tobia Sergel at Nationalmuseum
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1. Introduction

During 2023-2024, Nationalmuseum carried out a donor project about the conservation of one of Johan Tobias Sergel's (1740–1814) most iconic drawings, Hetsigt Kärlekspar. The drawing is made with iron gall ink on a thin Italian handmade ribbed paper and has extensive ink corrosion, which means that it cannot be exhibited. In addition to the original materials used by Sergel, the drawing was previously lined with an adhesive and support paper at an unknown date. This lining was however removed at a later date, but remnants of adhesive are still visible on the paper. The purpose of the guest colleague study was to better understand the composition of Hetsigt Kärlekspar, particularly the ink and the residual adhesive from the lining, which could perhaps lead to a better understanding of the fragile nature of the drawing and its deterioration processes.

For this study, Hetsigt Kärlekspar was placed in a broader context by also including several other drawings from the Sergel collection at Nationalmuseum. The chosen drawings were all dated to the same time period during Sergel's time in Rome after receiving a stipend in 1767. Despite the similarity in dates, the drawings have inks with varying tones (ranging from black to gray to dark and light brown), varying papers (differentiated by watermarks), different treatment histories (some have been lined, others not) and visible differences in condition (some show visible signs of iron gall ink corrosion, others do not). Including other drawings from the collection allowed for a more comparative study between different inks, papers and treatment practices to both improve the understanding of Hetsigt Kärlekspar and gain more insight into the collection materials. Analysis of the drawings was performed *in-situ* and non-invasively using x-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF). Additionally, a drawing with a lining present was sampled to analyze the adhesive using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR).

The areas of comparative study and questions related to them include:

1. Type of paper: are there differences in elemental composition between different types of paper?
2. Type of ink: are there differences in elemental composition between inks that appear visually different?
3. The lining: What is the lining adhesive made of? Does the lining affect the elemental composition of the drawings? Does residual lining adhesive on Hetsigt Kärlekspar affect its elemental composition?
4. Condition: are there noticeable differences in elemental composition of areas with visible iron gall ink corrosion and areas without?

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

Nine different drawings from Nationalmuseum's collection were chosen for analysis. All drawings were by Johan Tobias Sergel and dated from the same time period, during his travels to Rome after receiving a stipend in 1767. The drawings however have different characteristics (ink, paper, treatment). Images of the drawings as well as their names, inventory number, characteristics and analysis performed are presented in Table 1. All images were obtained from Nationalmuseum's online collection database and may not represent the colors visible on the actual documents. All drawings were analyzed *in-situ* using XRF. Additionally, the lining of NMH 582/1875 (Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom) was sampled for FTIR analysis to identify the lining adhesive. For sampling details, see the FTIR Instrumentrapport.

Table 1: Nine drawings by Johan Tobias Sergel chosen for analysis.

Drawing image	Description
	<p>Name: Hetsigt Kärlekspar Inventory #: NMH A 45/1970 Paper: Innocenzi and lion watermark Ink: Likely all iron gall ink Treatment: Previously lined, lining removed but adhesive still visible. Analysis: XRF point analysis, XRF mapping</p>
	<p>Name: Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom Inventory #: NMH 582/1875 Paper: Unknown Ink: Mixture of iron gall ink and non-vitriolic ink Treatment: Lined Analysis: XRF point analysis, XRF mapping, FTIR</p>

	<p>Name: Lucia, Sergels hushållerska Inventory #: NMH 544/1875 Paper: Unknown Ink: Likely all iron gall ink Treatment: None known Analysis: XRF point analysis, XRF mapping</p>
	<p>Name: Skulpturstudie Inventory #: NMH 1016/1875 Paper: Innocenzi and lion watermark Ink: Likely all iron gall ink Treatment: None known Analysis: XRF point analysis, XRF mapping</p>
	<p>Name: Signora Maria Sabastiani Inventory #: NMH 518/1875 Paper: Unknown Ink: Mixture iron gall ink and likely non-vitriolic / carbon-based ink Treatment: None known Analysis: XRF point analysis, XRF mapping</p>

Name: Menelaos och Patroklos
Inventory #: NMH 901/1875
Paper: Innocenzi and lion watermark
Ink: Likely all iron gall ink
Treatment: None known
Analysis: XRF point analysis, XRF mapping

Name: Söker Ensligheten
Inventory #: NMH 104/1906
Paper: Fleur-de-lis watermark
Ink: Likely all carbon-based ink
Treatment: None known
Analysis: XRF point analysis

Name: Stående manlig figur
Inventory #: NMH 586/1875
Paper: Fleur-de-lis watermark
Ink: Likely all carbon-based ink
Treatment: None known
Analysis: XRF point analysis

2.2. Instruments

To determine elemental composition of the drawings, XRF point analysis was performed on all nine drawings using a Bruker Artax 800 μ -XRF spectrometer. XRF mapping of the entirety of the following select drawings was performed using a Bruker Crono MA-XRF spectrometer: NMH A 45/1970, 582/1875, 544/1875, 1016/1875, 901/1875. Additionally, XRF mapping of a small area on NMH 582 was performed using a Bruker Artax 800 μ -XRF spectrometer. Details about the instrument parameters and analysis points can be found in the Artax μ XRF Instrumentrapport and the Crono MA-XRF Instrumentrapport.

To identify the adhesive used on the lining, ATR-FTIR analysis was performed on the sample removed from the lining on NMH 582/1875 using a Perkin Elmer Spectrum One spectrometer with a golden gate diamond ATR. Details about sampling, analysis locations and instrument parameters can be found in the FTIR Instrumentrapport.

3. Results and discussion

Type of paper

The elements present in all the papers were very similar with two exceptions: two of the papers with the Fleur-de-Lis watermark contained noticeable arsenic peaks, NMH 104/1906 and NMH 47/1906. It should however be noted that three of the drawings studied had Fleur-de-Lis watermarks while only two contained arsenic.

Besides these exceptions, only very small differences can be distinguished between the papers. Such small differences can be due to things like impurities and therefore cannot act as clear tracers for determining differences between different papers. Identified elements in the paper of each drawing are listed in Table 2. Example spectra showing a paper without arsenic peaks (NMH A 45/1970, Hetsigt Kärlekspar) and a paper with arsenic peaks (NMH 47/1906, Akilles med Patrokles lik) are presented in Figure 1. Individual spectra for all drawings can be found in the Artax μ XRF Instrumentrapport and its appendices.

Table 2: Elements found in the papers analyzed. The relative strength of the peaks is also indicated by the following letters: (s) strong, (m) moderate, (w) weak, (p) possible/only in localized spots.

Drawing	Peaks found in paper
NMH A 45/1970, Hetsigt Kärlekspar	Cl(w), K(m), Ca(m), Ti/Ba(p), Mn(w), Fe(w), Cu(w), Zn(w), Pb(p)
NMH 582/1875, Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom	Cl(w), K(w), Ca(m), Mn(w), Fe(w), Cu(w), Zn(w)
NMH 544/1875, Lucia, Sergels hushållerska	Cl(w), K(w), Ca(m), Mn(w), Fe(w), Cu(p), Zn(p)
NMH 1016/1875, Skulpturstudie	Cl(w), K(p), Ca(m), Mn(w), Fe(w), Cu(p)
NMH 518/1875, Signora Maria Sebastiani	Cl(w), K(w), Ca(m), Mn(w), Fe(w), Cu(p)
NMH 901/1875, Menelaos och Patroklos	Cl(w), K(w), Ca(m), Mn(w), Fe(w), Cu(p)
NMH 104/1906 Söker Ensligheten	Cl(w), K(w), Ca(m), Mn(w), Fe(w), Ni(p), Cu(p), Zn(p), As(w), Sr(w)
NMH 586/1875, Stående manlig figur	Cl(w), K(w), Ca(m), Mn(w), Fe(w), Cu(w), Zn(p)
NMH 47/1906 Akilles med Patrokles lik	K(w), Ca(w), Mn(w), Fe(w), Ni(w), Cu(p), Zn(p), As(m)

Figure 1: Spectra showing paper without arsenic (black, NMH 901/1875 Menelaos och Patroklos, pt. 8) and with arsenic (red, NMH 47/1906 Akilles med Patrokles lik, pt. 3). Spectra averaged and smoothed.

Type of ink

Possibly five different inks were identified by XRF analysis in the six drawings which were investigated by XRF mapping. Two of these inks are likely iron gall ink and three are likely carbon-based or non-vitriolic ink. The possible identified inks have the following general compositions:

Iron gall ink with mainly Fe, K and S present. Found in NMH 544/1875 (Lucia), NMH 1016/1875 (Skulpturstudie), NMH 518/1875 (Signora Maria Sebastiani) and NMH 901/1875 (Menelaos och Patroklos).

Iron gall ink with mainly Fe, K and S, with some elevated Ca. Found in NMH A 45/1970 (Hetsigt Kärlekspar), NMH 582/1875 (Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom), small singular areas of NMH 1016/1875 (Skulpturstudie) and in a brown wash in NMH 901/1875 (Menelaos och Patroklos). Ca is generally associated with the ink binder.

Non-vitriolic ink / Carbon ink. Found in NMH 518/1875 (Signora Maria Sebastiani).

Non-vitriolic / carbon ink with elevated K: Found on left side of NMH 518/1875 (Signora Maria Sebastiani). K is generally associated with the ink binder.

Non-vitriolic ink containing Fe, Pb and Si. Found in NMH 582/1875 (Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom).

It should be noted that many of the drawings have very thin lines which are difficult to analyze due to the available resolution of the instrument. The statements above are therefore based on analysis of areas with significant ink present and may not represent all ink lines.

Two drawings (NMH 582/1875 Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom, NMH 518/1875 Signora Maria Sebastiani) show evidence of both iron gall ink and non-vitriolic ink. The differences are also visually evident as all areas with a brownish tone showed evidence of iron gall ink, while all areas with a black or gray tone suggested a non-vitriolic ink. Generally, all solid lines drawn in NMH 582/1875 are iron gall ink while all washes are non-vitriolic. In NMH 518/1875, only the outline of the main figure (Maria Sebastiani) and some signatures are drawn in iron gall ink while the rest is non-vitriolic. The entirety of NMH 104/1906 Söker Ensligheten is drawn in carbon-based ink, while all remaining drawings (NMH A 45/1970 Hetsigt Kärlekspar, NMH 544/1875 Lucia, Sergels hushållerska, NMH 1016/1875 Skulpturstudie, NMH 901/1875 Menelaos och Patroklos, NMH 586/1875 Stående manlig figure, NMH 47/1906 Akilles med Patrokles lik) are drawn entirely in iron gall ink. Individual spectra for all drawings can be found in the Artax μ XRF Instrumentrapport and its appendices as well as the two Crono MA-XRF instrument reports.

Some of the areas of iron gall ink appeared to have slightly elevated calcium concentrations. This is most apparent in comparing the ink lines and brown wash of NMH 901/1875, spectra shown in Figure 2, in which it is clear that the brown wash contains elevated calcium. Additionally, maps showing the locations of both iron and calcium are shown in Figure 3, where it can be seen that the brown wash has a stronger calcium signal.

Figure 2: Spectra of ink lines (red fill), brown wash (yellow fill), gray wash (green fill) and paper (black line) on NMH 901/1875. See exact analysis locations in the Crono XRF Instrument report.

Figure 3: Image of NMH 901/1875 (left), map of calcium distribution (middle) and map of iron distribution (right).

The presence of calcium in gall ink is generally attributed to the gum-based binder (e.g. gum Arabic) which is often used, or possibly a previous conservation treatment using for example calcium phytate. Studies by Remazeilles on contemporary mockups and historical documents showed that gum Arabic may delay the weakening of the paper (Remazeilles 2004, Remazeilles 2005). However, if the binder itself begins to degrade, then this may allow for the free migration of iron ions into the paper, thus leading to greater probability of paper corrosion (Remazeilles 2005). Remazeilles also noted in historical documents a correlation between potassium content and document condition, in which higher potassium concentrations correlated to better preservation states. Potassium is also attributed most commonly to the gum binder in the ink. No significant correlations between potassium content, calcium content and document condition could be clearly found in the documents studied.

Besides possible small differences in calcium content, all the iron-gall inks used in the drawings are composed primarily of iron with sulfur and potassium. This may suggest that a particular type of vitriol, with the trade name vitriolum romanum, was used to create the ink. This vitriol was noted to contain a high concentration of iron sulfate, no zinc sulfate, and very little (around 2%) copper sulfate (Gerken et al. 2022, Hickel 1963). A study by Hickel located a mining site for vitriolum romanum on the island of Elba (Hickel 1963), while a study by Krekel investigated historical pharmaceutical documents describing sources from Umbria, Tuscany and Bagnorea (Krekel et al. 2005). Vitriolum romanum was also known to be exported outside Italy, as it was found that significant amounts were imported into Germany (Krekel et al. 2005).

The spectra for non-vitriolic inks in different drawings appear different from each other and may indicate different inks. In NMH 582/1875 Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom, both the black and gray inks have consistent lead peaks throughout the drawing. However, lead peaks are only present in some sporadic spectra in NMH 518/1875 Signora Maria Sebastiani, suggesting rather that it is an occasional impurity in this drawing. Furthermore, the non-vitriolic inks used in both NMH 582/1875 and NMH 518/1875 show evidence of some iron while NMH 104/1906 Söker Ensligheten does not other than the iron found in the blank paper. Figure 4a shows example spectra from both NMH 582/1875 and NMH 518/1875 while 3b compares the blank paper to the ink in NMH 104/1906. These small differences could suggest three different carbon-based inks, but the differences could also be from contaminants in receptacles or from accidental blending with other inks.

Figure 4: Spectra comparing (a) lead peaks in areas of black ink from NMH 582/1875 Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom (black, pt. 20) and NMH 518/1875 Signora Maria Sebastiani (red, pt. 23 and blue, pt. 24); (b) black ink (black, pt. 1) and paper (red, pt.2) in NMH 104/1906 Söker Ensligheten. All spectra are averaged and smoothed.

Lining adhesive

The lining paper adhesive on NMH 582/1875 Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom shows the presence of calcium, potassium and sulfur. Other peaks are from the lining paper, suggesting that the adhesive is primarily organic. Areas on NMH A 45/1970 Hetsigt Kärlekspar with and without adhesive residue were investigated with XRF and found no significant differences in the spectra. Figure 5a and b shows the results.

Figure 5: Spectra of (a) an area of the yellowing adhesive selected on the Crono map of the top of NMH 582/1875 Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom and (b) paper without adhesive residue (black, pt. 1) and with adhesive residue (red, pt. 3) on NMH A 45/1970 Hetsigt Kärlekspar. All spectra are averaged and smoothed.

Similar signals were detected on other drawings, suggesting that these drawings may have residual adhesive from a previous lining. These drawings include NMH 544/1875 and NMH 518/1875, both of which have distinct lines across the top of the drawings that contain potassium, sulfur and calcium. There is also significant sulfur signal on the right side of NMH 518, possibly suggesting an adhesive in this location as well. Figure 6 shows the XRF maps of these documents as well as their K, S and Ca signals.

Figure 6: Elemental maps of calcium, sulfur and potassium in NMH 518/1875 (top) and NMH 544/1875 (bottom), showing similar elemental composition along the top edges, suggesting that the same adhesive may be present as on NMH 582/1875.

FTIR was also used to investigate the adhesive on a sample taken from NMH 582/1875 Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom, but no differences were found between the spectrum of the plain lining paper and the spectrum of the paper with visible, yellowing adhesive present (Figure 7). All visible peaks correlate to the cellulose structure of the paper. This may be because the signal from the paper is much stronger than that of the adhesive, thus completely overshadowing peaks from the adhesive and making them difficult to identify. Other forms of analysis (e.g. GC-MS) may be more applicable for this material. For more details about sampling and measurement areas, consult the FTIR Instrumentrapport.

Figure 7: Overlaid FTIR spectra of the paper with adhesive (black), paper without adhesive (red) and a reference spectrum of VWR light duty tissue wipers (blue).

Paper support on Lucia (NMH 544/1875)

Visual observation of the right side of NMH 544/1875 suggests that two different papers have been added to the original document. This information is corroborated by the XRF data which displays differences in elemental composition between the original document and the two added papers (see Figure 6, bottom). An initial strip of paper adhered directly to the original document shows the presence of potassium and some sulfur, of which both elements are strongest at the interface of the original document and the added paper. This latter information can suggest the presence of an adhesive and can indicate an earlier intervention. There is also a noticeable lack of calcium. The second layer of paper added further to the right of the document shows calcium but less potassium and sulfur, correlating more clearly to the paper strips adhered to the other edges of the document, likely a later intervention.

Condition

There is a possible correlation between iron peak heights and iron gall ink corrosion. The drawings which show evidence of corrosion are NMH A 45/1970 Hetsigt Kärlekspar, NMH 544/1875 Lucia Sergels hushållerska and NMH 901/1875 Menelaos och Patroklos. When comparing spectra of dark iron gall ink lines between the documents in this study, it appears that the three drawings which exhibit visible corrosion have higher iron peaks and thus higher iron concentrations than the drawings without visible corrosion. One exception is NMH 1016/1875 Skulpturstudie, which has high iron peaks but does not show clear signs of visible corrosion.

Figure 8a shows spectra from areas of dark, non-corroded iron gall ink lines on all drawings where iron gall ink was studied. Additionally, Figure 8b compares areas of corrosion on the drawings exhibiting this phenomenon. In all cases, the corroded areas have smaller iron peaks compared to the non-corroded areas on the same drawing, however this could be due to loss of material as a result of the corrosion process.

Figure 8: Spectra showing (a) non-corroded dark ink lines from NMH A 45/1970 (black, pt. 7), NMH 582/1875 (red, pt. 17), NMH 544/1875 (blue, pt. 17), NMH 1016/1875 (green, pt. 8), NMH 518/1875 (yellow, pt. 26), NMH 901/1875 (purple, pt. 13) and (b) corroded dark ink lines from NMH A 45/1970, (black, pt. 10), NMH 544/1875 (blue, pt. 16), NMH 901/1875 (purple, pt.16). All spectra are averaged.

Mend on Hetsigt Kärlekspar

Two mended areas which were intended to fill losses in corroded parts of Hetsigt Kärlekspar were investigated to determine the composition of the mend materials. Compared to the original document, the mended locations have noticeable Zn, Ba or Ti peaks, and some possible small Cr peaks. It also appears that mended areas possibly have slightly elevated Pb compared to the ink. These elements possibly indicate the presence of a colorant containing fillers with zinc oxide, barium sulfate and calcium. Figure 9 shows comparative spectra taken both directly on a mend and in an area of the drawing adjacent to the mend.

Figure 9: Spectra showing measurement directly on a mend (black, pt. 13) and measurement on ink near a mend (red, pt. 15) on NMH A 45/1970 Hetsigt Kärlekspar. All spectra are averaged.

4. Conclusions

Nine drawings by Johan Tobias Sergel in the collection at Nationalmuseum were investigated using x-ray fluorescence spectroscopy and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The primary drawing of focus was Hetsigt Kärlekspar with the intention to better understand its material composition (both original and added later through conservation treatment) in relation to other collection drawings and how this composition can potentially affect its condition.

The elemental compositions of the different papers were very similar with the exception of two papers bearing the Fleur-de-lis watermark which contained arsenic peaks. Otherwise, all papers contained traces of primarily chlorine, potassium, calcium, magnesium, iron and copper.

Both iron gall ink and likely carbon-based / non-vitriolic ink were identified amongst the nine drawings. Possibly five different inks were identified amongst the collection of drawings. Some of these differences, however, depend on the strength of the calcium and potassium peaks, both of which are generally associated with the ink binder. Two drawings (NMH 582/1875 Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom and NMH 518/1875 Signora Maria Sebastiani) contain both types of inks; NMH 104/1906 Söker Ensligheten is composed entirely of non-vitriolic ink; and the remaining drawings are composed of only iron gall ink. The iron gall inks used contain primarily iron, sulfur and potassium without any strong indication of other common elements like copper or zinc. This may suggest that Sergel was using an ink containing a type of vitriol with the trade name vitriolum romanum. The carbon-based inks showed clearer differences, some of which contained traces of lead (NMH 582/1875 Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom), some which had no elemental traces at all (NMH 104/1906 Söker Ensligheten), and some which showed elevated potassium levels (NMH 518/1875 Signora Maria Sebastiani). However, it is difficult to determine if the differences are actually due to the use of different inks or if they are due to some form of contamination (e.g. from the ink receptacles).

The exact adhesive used with the lining on NMH A 45/1970 Hetsigt Kärlekspar and NMH 582/1875 Sergel saltar in oxtungor i Rom could not be identified with the instruments used in this study. However, sulfur, potassium and calcium were identified as main elements in the yellowing adhesive on NMH 582/1875. Similar yellowing adhesives on edges of both NMH 518/1875 and NMH 544/1875 were identified with similar elemental compositions. Other analytical tools, such as gas chromatography-mass spectrometry may be useful for better identification of the adhesive.

In general, drawings which showed evidence of iron gall ink corrosion tend to have higher concentrations of iron in the ink. As no other clear differences were found between the iron-based inks or the papers in the studied collection, a possible theory for the fragile nature of Hetsigt Kärlekspar can lie in its higher concentrations of iron in the ink. In general, it is accepted that the corrosion process is due to the presence of free Fe^{2+} ions in the paper and that papers with pH values exhibit more significant corrosion. The difference between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions in ink cannot be detected by XRF but can be detected by other tools which often require sampling such as Mössbauer spectroscopy and X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure (XANES) spectroscopy.

The conditions of the drawings and the level of corrosive behavior exhibited by the inks can be influenced by a number of features of the document, including the ink composition, the thickness and sizing of the paper, the amount of gum Arabic used as a binder in the inks, the thickness of the ink lines and previous storage conditions. Using XRF non-invasively cannot identify all of these differences in the documents. Such an investigation would likely require sampling and involve analysis using FTIR, GC-MS, Raman spectroscopy and other techniques. While there may be reason for the fragile nature of Hetsigt Kärlekspar, identifying such a reason would require further investigation with other instrumentation.

5. Storage

Raw data from the project is stored on Riksantikvarieämbetet's raw data database Lida (L:). Project documentation is stored under its diarienummer on the internal network G: and in Platina, as well as physically in Riksantikvarieämbetet's archives.

Raw data, instrument reports and the analysis report were uploaded to the data repository Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14850918> (raw data and instrument reports); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851050> (analysis report).

6. References

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